

Supplementary Figure 2: A) *Fd-GOGAT* gene exon/intron structure from different organisms. The number of bp of each gene, the number of exons and the corresponding organisms are indicated. B) *NADH-GOGAT* gene exon/intron structure from different organisms. The number of bp of each gene, the number of exons and the corresponding organisms are indicated. In both diagrams, exons are in orange and introns in black.

A) *Fd-GOGAT*

B) *NADH-GOGAT*

